

THE ROLE OF FAMILY IN CHILDREN'S EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

The family is one of the important elements in society and education; of course, because it is about it. The importance of the family is to guide or to orientation the people who are part of it in order to obtain or guide a more efficient and useful life path

A kid's education starts from home. Parents are their first teachers and they have a key role in shaping up their character. A balance of education at home and school moulds a student's actual learning. Be a helping hand in their educational journey and travel with them with true inspiration. Parental encouragement had played a crucial role in successful students. Their role is not limited to home but involvement in school activities too. A child's learning scale is highly related to how they are treated at home. Here are a few ways which parents can adopt to help with their child's education:

1. Be a role model

Kids would be easily inspired by what their parents do. So it would be good to be a role model in their learning phase. Parents are a kid's first teachers and so learn the first things together at home. Show them how exciting and meaningful a school life can be if they give out their best. Inspire them to learn novel elements in and out of school with friendly reminders and guidance.

2. Read together

Doing things together with parents give them a sense of support and confidence.

Reading the lessons together is one of the best ways to be close with the child's learning at school. This not only improves their vocabulary but invokes interest in them to read more. It is also a good idea to visit the library together and share quality books to help them get additional knowledge than classroom lessons.

3. Oversee child's activity

It is important to have an eye on the child's activity in school and home. Their general habits are closely linked to how they perform in their studies.

So give timely advice and correct any abnormal behavior right from the childhood days and inspire them to be good citizens. Help them to be more organized with their daily routine and find enough time for the lessons.

4. No over scheduling

It is not a good idea to over schedule them with learning activities at home.

They are spending about half of their day at school. So help them schedule their extra learning and homework time at home without burdening them.

Balancing the time between lessons, play time and rest is important to have a quality student life.

5. Provide pleasant atmosphere

Parents should make sure that the kids are provided with a peaceful and pleasant atmosphere at home. It is good to avoid discussing family problems in kid's presence and don't create a mess at home with unnecessary quarrels. Both father and mother should consider the importance of their study life and give them adequate moral support.

6. Give constructive criticism

If you notice that your kid is not performing well or giving less importance to studies, correct them at the beginning itself. However, it is not good to spoil their peace of mind with ill words. Have some patience and give only constructive criticism if you notice any downsides. Make them understand what is right and wrong rather than simply blaming them.

7. Help with home assignments

Giving good support to kids in their studies would really lift their spirit for learning. Show it with small gestures such as helping them with home assignments or projects. However, it is not advised to do every lesson for them and let them play. Do it together and help them with some tips and guidance in doing the assignments better.

8. Reward them for results

Giving good motivation is important for a kid to perform better with studies.

So don't hesitate to reward them if they come up with some good results in the tests. This also gives them the spirit to perform better every next time.

However, keep a limit and it is not good to over shower them with gifts for an average performance which fades away their killer instinct.

9. Go for educational trips

It is a good idea to go for educational trips during the holidays. Include destinations that have some relevance with what they are studying to help them have a better understanding of the lessons. Occasional trips to museums and zoos would also help them to interact with the nature and learn new things.

"Society is a group of people who occupy an area, bound by the same experiences, and can act together to meet the crisis of life. Public relations plays an important role in helping the effectiveness of tasks in school management." The function of education in the community is to prepare the younger generation to play certain roles in society in the future, transferring knowledge related to these roles from the older generation to the younger generation, and moving the values that aim to maintain the need and community unity which is an absolute condition for the continuation of the life of a society and civilization. According to Edwin B. Flippo, "Education is an increase in general knowledge and understanding of our environment as a whole, while training is an effort to increase the knowledge and expertise of an employee to do a particular job." In understanding a family, the family has several meanings. The family is a social group consisting of two or more people who have blood ties, marriage, or adoption. "Thus it can be taken an essence of understanding of the family, namely:

1) the family is the smallest social group which generally consists of father, mother and child,

2) social relations where the family is relatively fixed are based on blood ties, marriage or adoption,

3) the relationship between families is inspired by the arrangement of affection and sense of responsibility, and

4) the function of the family is to restore, care for, and protect children in the context of socialization so that they are able to control themselves and have a social spirit." In terms of education, the family is a unit of life (social system), and the family provides learning situations. As a unit of living together (social system), the family consists of father, mother and child. Family ties help children develop the nature of friendship, love, interpersonal relationships, cooperation, discipline, good behavior, and recognition of authority. Meanwhile, with regard to families providing a learning situation it can be seen that babies and children are very dependent on parents, both from their physical condition and intellectual, social, and moral abilities. Babies and children learn to imitate what their parents teach. As the first and foremost education, "Family education can print children to have personalities which can then be developed in subsequent institutions, so that the authority of these institutions does not change what they already have in the wearer, but enough by combining the education obtained from the family with the family pendidian, so that mosques, Islamic boarding schools, and schools are transitional places of family education." "Family donations for children's education are as follows:

1) the way parents train their children to master ways to take care of themselves, walk, pray, truly imprint on themselves because they are closely related to their personal development;

2) The attitude of parents greatly influences children's development. The

attitude of accepting or rejecting, the attitude of compassion or indifference, patience or haste, the attitude of protecting or letting directly affect the child's emotional reaction." It is natural and logical if education is in the hands of parents and cannot be carried by others because it is the blood of the flesh, except for the limitations of these two parents. So, as the responsibility of education can be delegated to others, namely through school. The educational responsibilities that need to be based and nurtured by both parents of children include:

a) maintaining and raising it, this responsibility is a natural impetus to be carried out because the person needs to eat, drink and care so that he will continue to live sustainably,

b) protect and guarantee their health, both religiously and spiritually, from various diseases or environmental hazards that can endanger themselves,

c) educate him with a variety of knowledge and skills that are useful for his life so that if he is an adult he can stand alone and help others, and d) giving them religious education. The awareness of the responsibility of educating and fostering children continuously needs to be developed for every parent so that the education they do is no longer based on the habits seen from parents, but the age-old people who tend to change. The main task of the family in education is as a foundation for moral education and religious outlook. The characteristics of children are mostly taken from their parents and other family members.

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